

CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS

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Abstract: This thesis is devoted to the analysis of the processes of improving the professional competence of future music teachers. The thesis examines the concept of professional competence and its role in music education. Also, the mechanisms of professional skills development through the use of innovative approaches to teacher training, advanced pedagogical technologies and modern methods will be covered in detail. The authors suggest ways to organize creative and pedagogical activities of teachers more effectively. These mechanisms contribute to the professional growth of future teachers and their personal development.

Key words: Future music teachers, professional competence, improvement mechanisms, pedagogical technologies, music education, innovative approaches.

Introduction:

One of the main tasks of the modern education system is to develop and improve the professional competence of future teachers. In particular, the training of music teachers depends not only on musical knowledge and skills, but also on their pedagogical skills, creative approach, and the ability to use modern technologies. Future music teachers need to have such professional training that allows them not only to teach music, but also to arouse interest in the art of music in students, and to help them in their personal and creative development.

Today, the competence approach occupies an important place in the education system, because the formation of a teacher's professional competence has a direct impact on his success in the educational process and the level of knowledge of students. Therefore, it is important to introduce new pedagogical technologies and use innovative methods in the process of professional training of future music teachers. In this thesis, the content and essence of improving the professional competence of music teachers, and the mechanisms of their development are extensively analyzed.

Analysis of foreign literature:

The issue of developing the professional competence of future music teachers is widely studied at the international level. The researches of foreign scientists show that the professional qualifications, creative abilities and

technological literacy of music education teachers have a direct impact on their educational effectiveness. In particular, in the USA and European countries, the competence approach is considered relevant in the training of music teachers, and integrative and multidisciplinary approaches are used in the training of teachers[3, p.136].

For example, the researches of J. Davidson[2, p.235] and S. Jordan provide important practical recommendations for the use of a person-oriented approach and innovative pedagogical technologies in music education. According to them, music teachers should be focused not only on imparting music knowledge, but also on creative thinking, development of aesthetic taste and increasing students' interest with the help of technology. From this point of view, it is recommended to combine creative and didactic approaches for the professional development of future music teachers.

Another important research was conducted by A. Burnard[1, p.85] and V. Ross, who emphasize the effectiveness of reflective pedagogy and reflective teaching methods in training future music teachers. Through these approaches, the teacher can deeply analyze the students' learning process and understand his professional growth. Also, the widespread use of digital technologies opens the door to new opportunities for future teachers, helping to make the process of music education interactive and effective.

According to the experience of Sweden[4, p.45] and Finland[5, p.235], technological literacy is an important factor for music teachers. In their research, the use of digital tools in the training of music teachers, for example, interactive organization of lessons with the help of musical programs and platforms, is noted as one of the main directions.

In general, the individualization of the educational process, the use of digital technologies, and the development of professional competence through creativity and reflective approaches in the training of future music teachers on the analysis of foreign literature are relevant methods. Studying foreign experience and adapting it to the national education system is of great importance for improving the quality of musical education.

Discussion:

The mechanisms of improving the professional competence of future music teachers are seen as important pedagogical processes. The analysis of foreign literature shows that the competence approach in training pedagogues and teachers is one of the most effective methods, it helps to improve the

professional skills of teachers, arouse interest in music art in students, as well as creative and analytical thinking. is the main factor in the development of skills.

In the educational system of Uzbekistan, it is important to introduce innovative methods and technologies in the development of professional competence of future music teachers. In this case, it is necessary to use active and interactive teaching methods in the educational process, to create opportunities for teachers' self-development and professional development. For example, it is possible to increase the level of competence of teachers by introducing them to modern music technologies, conducting practices on the organization of musical resources, lessons and extracurricular activities on online platforms.

Also, in order to develop creative approaches of teachers, it is necessary to develop programs aimed at forming their individual approaches to students and developing their abilities. For this, it is important to introduce a mentoring system in educational institutions, to create opportunities to study together with highly qualified teachers and share experience.

The need to use innovative approaches in the assimilation of foreign experiences, in the development of programs for the professional development of teachers, in the modernization of methodical materials, and in the support of the creative activities of students in the educational process is an important issue. Innovative methods used in the educational process, such as collaborative teaching, problem-based approach and experiential learning, have a significant impact on improving the professional competence of teachers.

It contributes to the introduction of mechanisms for improving professional competence in the music education system of Uzbekistan, increasing the level of professionalism of teachers and improving the educational efficiency of students. Such an approach will certainly allow future music teachers to perform their duties effectively and increase their interest in learning the art of music. This, in turn, serves as an important factor in improving the quality of music education.

Conclusion:

In this thesis, the mechanisms of improving the professional competence of future music teachers and their content and essence were analyzed. The results of the research show that the competence approach, innovative pedagogical technologies and modern teaching methods play an important role in improving the professional skills of future teachers. Foreign experiences also confirm the

need to use digital technologies and develop creative thinking skills in the educational process.

At the same time, it is important to individualize the pedagogical process and develop programs aimed at the personal development of teachers in the training of future music teachers in the educational system of Uzbekistan. The experiences and innovative approaches of teachers, as well as the introduction of a mentoring system, support their professional development and help to form an individual approach to students.

Innovative methods used in the educational process, for example, collaborative teaching and problem-based approaches, serve as effective tools for improving the level of competence of music teachers. This, in turn, increases interest in learning the art of music and encourages students to create.

In general, the mechanisms for improving the professional competence of future music teachers serve to introduce innovative approaches to teacher training and increase the quality of education. Such an approach certainly ensures that music education meets modern requirements and creates an opportunity to introduce the future generation to the art of music.

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